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A STUDY OF ORGANIZATION LEARNING IN SOUTH INDIAN AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRIES

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Abstract

Objective- In today's world of ever-increasing competition, organizations are forced to look for new ways to improve their performance. Firms are increasingly focusing on the concept of organizational learning to increase their competitive advantage, innovation, and effectiveness. The study aims to examine the impact of organizational learning on organizational performance of south Indian automobile industries.

Design/Methodology/Approach- The paper is conceptualized and is based on primary data collected from employees working in the manufacturing department of automobile companies. Research instrument development was preceded by focus group discussions.

Findings- Senge model in this study shows that system thinking, team learning, building shared vision, mental models and personal mastery have an influence on Organization learning and Organization performance.

Limitations- The study was cross sectional and that was a limitation. A longitudinal study would have helped study the impact of organization intervention on learning and performance. The limitation to Senge's model was also a limitation as other factors contributing to organization learning and performance were not in the purview of this study.

Practical Implications- The paper shows the relevance of Senge's learning model in the automobile industry. The aspects of system thinking, team learning, building shared vision, mental models and personal mastery are factors that organizations should focus on during training, appraisals and managing productivity.

Originality/value- The paper is an original contribution to the field of organization learning and performance in the automobile industry in the South Indian context. Having practically applied Senge's model to the South Indian automobile industry it proves the validity of the model in this industry and this part of the world.

Keywords: Organization learning, organization performance, India, South India, Automobile Industry, Senge

Introduction:

In the past decade, technological innovation is evidently shown to play a crucial role in the international competition. Hence, scientific and technological capacity decides the export performance of the country (Drucker, 1999). Senge (1990), suggests that a building up of a continuous learning and improvement -based organization is the best way to keep up with the competition. Senge also suggest that further argues that Organization Learning (OL) controls many factors of an organization that includes manufacturing activities also.

In spite of the crucial requirement of theoretical models, organizational learning and technological advance are important qualification to study the dynamic process of capability building and consequently inform the policy makers on the design of appropriate strategies for industrial progress. Thus, the need was felt in the present study to examine the impact of organizational learning on the organizational performance of South Indian automobile industries.

Senge (1990) defined OL as a “Continuous testing of experience and its transformation into knowledge available to whole organization and relevant to their mission”.

According to Senge (1990) learning organizations are: organizations wherein people continuously develop their capability to invent the desired results; where novel and expansive patterns of thinking are cultivated, where there is freedom for collective ambition, and where people are continuously learning to perceive the whole together. The five component technologies five that Senge (1990) identified are Systems thinking, Personal mastery, mental models, Building shared vision, Team learning.

In this respect, several studies applied OL in technology intensive industries as a main factor to maintain innovation. The model is shown in Figure 1. This Senge model has the capacity to react to the changes in the external environment, and then provide the source to alter and change the existing rules and strategies.

By utilizing the Senge (1990) model, the present study applies the model in automobile industry.

Objective:

1. To study the impact of the various components; Systems thinking, Personal mastery, mental models, Building shared vision, Team learning, on Organizational Learning and Organizational Performance.

Research Methodology:

The present empirical research study was based on data collected from Indian automobile manufacturing industries. For the purpose, the random sampling method was employed not only to select a representative sample but also to minimize sample error in the study. The questionnaires were given to 400 participants in South India. Only 335 participants completed with a response rate of 84.0 per cent. The data collection was made using paper-pencil method and email with gentle reminder calls to the participants.

The research instrument in this study was a structured Closed-Ended questionnaire with 59-items to measure the employee's perceptions on learning organization. The questionnaire was developed based on the concept of five key disciplines proposed by Senge's (Senge, 1990) model. The questionnaire was classified into 6 segments, namely: Systems Thinking, Mental model, Building Shared Vision, Team Learning, Personal Mastery they are considered as independent variables, whereas Organizational performance is taken as dependent variable in the study.

Analysis:

Objective . To study the impact of the various components; Systems thinking, Personal mastery, mental models, Building shared vision, Team learning, on Organizational Learning and Organizational Performance.

The variables used in the structural equation model are

- I. Observed, endogenous variables
 1. Systems Thinking
 2. Mental Models
 3. Building Shared Vision
 4. Team Learning
 5. Personal Mastery
 6. Organizational Performance

- II. Unobserved, exogenous variables
 1. Organizational Learning
 2. e1: Error term for Systems Thinking
 3. e2: Error term for Mental Models
 4. e3: Error term for Building Shared Vision
 5. e4: Error term for Team Learning
 6. e5: Error term for Personal Mastery
 7. e6: Error term for Organizational Performance

Hence number of variable in the SEM is

Number of variables in this model	13
Number of observed variables	6
Number of unobserved variables	7
Number of exogenous variables	7
Number of endogenous variables	6

Fig. 1 SEM on Organizational Learning in Automobile Industries

Here the coefficient of **Systems Thinking** is 0.408 represents the partial effect of System Thinking on Organizational Learning, holding the other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organizational Learning would increase by 0.408 for every unit increase in System Thinking and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of **Mental Models** is 0.351 represents the partial effect of Mental Models on Organizational Learning, holding the other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organizational Learning would increase by 0.351 for every unit increase in Mental Models and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of **Building Shared Vision** is 0.336 represents the partial effect of Building Shared

Table 1: Variables in the Structural Equation Model Analysis

Variables		Un-standarised co-efficient	S.E	Standardised co-efficient	t value	P value	
Systems Thinking	←	Organizational Learning	0.408	0.031	0.758	13.300	<0.001*
Mental Models	←	Organizational Learning	0.351	0.050	0.642	7.054	<0.001*
Building Shared Vision	←	Organizational Learning	0.336	0.029	0.650	11.448	<0.001*
Team Learning	←	Organizational Learning	0.401	0.054	0.795	7.435	<0.001*
Personal Mastery	←	Organizational Learning	0.388	0.030	0.725	12.731	<0.001*
Organizational Performance	←	Organizational Learning	0.177	0.035	0.298	5.103	<0.001*

Note: 1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level

2. * Denotes significant at 5% level

Vision on Organizational Learning, holding the other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organizational Learning would increase by 0.336 for every unit increase in Building Shared Vision and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of **Team Learning** is 0.401 represents the partial effect of Team Learning on Organizational Learning, holding the other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organizational Learning would increase by 0.401 for every unit increase in Team Learning and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. The coefficient of **Personal Mastery** is 0.388 represents the partial effect of Personal Mastery on Organizational Learning, holding the other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organizational Learning would increase by 0.388 for every unit increase in Personal Mastery and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level and The coefficient of **Organizational Performance** is 0.177 represents the partial effect of Organizational Learning on Organization Performance, holding the other variables as

constant. The estimated positive sign implies that such effect is positive that Organization Performance would increase by 0.177 for every unit increase in Organizational Learning and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level.

Table 2: Model fit summary

Variable	Value	Suggested value
Chi-square value	4.553	
P value	0.208	P-value >0.05 (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p. 1-700)
GFI	0.996	>0.90 (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p. 1-700)
AGFI	0.969	> 0.90 (Hooper, Coughlan & Mullen, 2008, p. 53-60)
CFI	0.998	>0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999, p. 1-55)
RMR	0.005	< 0.08 (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p. 1-700)
RMSEA	0.039	< 0.08 (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p. 1-700)

From the above table it is found that the calculated P value is 0.208 which is greater than 0.05 which indicates perfectly fit (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p 1-700). Here GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) value (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p 1-700) and AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) value (Hooper, Coughlan & Mullen, 2008, p. 53-60) is greater than 0.9 which represent it is a good fit. The calculated CFI (Comparative Fit Index) value is 0.998 which means that it is a perfectly fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999, p. 1-55) and also it is found that RMR (Root Mean Square Residuals) and RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) value is 0.005 & 0.039, which is less than 0.08 which indicated it is perfectly fit (Hair, Bush & Ortinau, 2006, p 1-700).

Conclusion:

Based on SEM analysis, the coefficient of Organizational Performance is 0.177, which represents the Organization Performance would increase by 0.177 for every unit increase in Organizational Learning and this coefficient value is significant at 1% level. In a learning

organization, people are constantly developing their capacities to attain the favorable results. New modes of learning develop the needs and other requirements of groups are realized, moreover employees understood how to learn things together (Senge, 1990,; Fallah, Amirtash & Mozaffari, 2010). A causal relationship exists between organizational learning and performance (Jyothibabu, Farooq and Pradhan ,2010; Yang, Wang & Niu, 2007). Similarly, a positive relationship between organizational learning and firm performance also exists and many authors have supported this (Bontis, Crossan & Hulland, 2002,; García-Morales,Lloréns-Montes & Verdú-Jover, 2008; Jiménez-Jiménez & Sanz-Valle, 2011). Organizations learn more effectively from failures than successes, that knowledge from failure depreciates more slowly than knowledge from success, and that prior stocks of experience and the magnitude of failure influence how effectively organizations can learn from various forms of experience.

The findings from this study provided additional evidence to that reported in other literature namely that organizational learning positively and significantly influences SME organizational performance (Alegre & Chiva 2008; Goh & Ryan 2008; Panagiotakopoulos, 2011). The findings from this study also provided a different viewpoint in regard to the influence of SME organizational learning on SME performance since it used a different set of indicators of organizational learning and performance to those used in other studies. The learning and sharing of knowledge enhanced turnover, yielded higher profits and as well extended the product. In Spain, SME producers of ceramics, displayed that risk taking, experimentation, dialogue and participative decision making and interaction with the external environment, influenced organizational performance when it is measured as a product innovation's enhancement (Alegre and Chiva, 2008). SMEs of Greece discovered that a continuous effort to accomplish and manipulate knowledge in SME organizations possesses an important influence on survival and growth of SME (Panagiotakopoulos, 2011).

Present study applies conceptual frameworks of organizational learning and adaptation to a specific industry to determine if there is validity to the concept of organizational learning. Present empirical research has shown the positive impact of Systems Thinking, Mental Model, Building Shared vision, Team Learning, Personal Mastery on organizational performance

Limitations/Scope for future work:

Present study was only conducted in performance of automobile industry in South Indian region. For wider applicability of the findings it should be expanded to a broader geographical context preferably in the countries at different development stages. Also longitudinal analysis of the relationship between constructs should be performed to determine if there is a time lag in construct correlation. There is a lack of empirical research into how organizational learning influences organizational performance, SMEs context and in regard to the India context.

There is a need to enhance SME commitment to organizational learning practices. The results from this study showed that organizational learning leads to better organizational performance. To further validate our findings, a case study in a company should be performed. This would give us deeper understanding of the relationship of the constructs proposed in the present model and would serve to further test its applicability and usefulness from the practical point of view. Large firm management is fundamentally different from SME management and the conclusions that have been drawn from many studies of organizational learning in large enterprises cannot be applied to SMEs without empirical confirmation and more research on SMEs should be performed.

This study has focused on only limited factors in organizational learning. However, since India has long traditional background, there can be several other factors that help to achieve organizational performance. Hence, further researches can focus on other contributing factors that affect the organization learning and in turn organisational performance of the industry.

References:

- Alegre, J, & Chiva, R, 2008, 'Assessing the impact of organizational learning capability on product innovation performance: An empirical test', *Technovation*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 315-326
- Bontis, N, Crossan, M & Hulland, J 2002, 'Managing an organizational learning system by aligning stocks and flows', *Journal of Management Studies*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 437-469
- Drucker, P 1999, *The new Realities*, Heinemann, New York, NY, pp. 1- 274.
- Fallah, Z & Amirtash, AM & Mozaffari, M 2010, 'Comparative Study of Attitude In the Physical Education', *TTEM journal*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 226-232

- García-Morales, VJ, Lloréns-Montes, FJ & Verdú-Jover, AJ 2008, 'The Effects of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Performance through Knowledge and Innovation', *British Journal of Management*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 299–319.
- Goh, SC & Ryan, PJ 2008, 'The organizational performance of learning companies - a longitudinal and competitor analysis using market and accounting financial data', *The Learning Organization*, vol. 15, no.3, pp. 225-239.
- Jiménez-Jiménez, D & Sanz-Valle, R 2011, 'Innovation, organizational learning, and performance', *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 64, no. 4, pp. 408–417.
- Hair, JF, Bush, RP & Ortinau, DJ 2006, *Marketing research: within a changing information environment*, 3rd ed., McGraw-Hill, Boston, pp. 1-700
- Hooper, D, Coughlan, J, Mullen, M (2008), 'Structural Equation Modelling: Guidelines for Determining Model Fit', *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 53-60.
- Hu, L & Bentler, PM 1999, 'Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives', *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–55.
- Jyothibabu, C, Farooq, A & Bhusan Pradhan, B 2010, 'An integrated scale for measuring an organizational learning system', *The Learning Organization*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 303–327.
- Panagiotakopoulos, A 2011, 'Workplace learning and its organizational benefits for small enterprises – evidence from Greek Industrial firms', *The Learning Organization*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 364-374.
- Senge, P. (1990), "The leader's new work: Building learning organization", Sloan management review, pp. 7–23.
- Yang, C, Wang, Y-D & Niu, H-J 2007, 'Does Industry Matter in Attributing Organizational Learning to its Performance?: Evidence from the Taiwanese Economy', *Asia Pacific Business Review*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 547–563

About the Author:

The author Dr. Ashvini Ravi has a MBA from the premier institute S.P.Jain Institute of Management & Research. She completed her PhD in management studies in the year 2004. She has 10 years of industrial experience working in the management cadre of several organizations. Her brief stint in online learning and content development has given her the experience of teaching management to students online and also developing management content in a variety of subjects. She has more than 15 years of academic experience; teaching, training, mentoring and guiding MBA students.